

White Paper

Accelerating Digital Healthcare Transformation in Nigeria: A White Paper on the Prospects of a Policy-Aligned Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework, the Cloud-Based and Voice-Enabled TUMERIC, and the TUMERIC Cloud Network Model

Target Audience: Policy Makers and Regulatory Bodies (MoH, FMOH, NITDA, WHO, WB, AfDB, ECOWAS), Healthcare Institutions (UTHs, HCPs, NGOs), Technology & Industry (ICT, Cloud, Startups), Knowledge & Funding Partners (Academia, Donors, Impact Investors)

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1. Abstract

Nigeria's healthcare system remains constrained by fragmented paper-based records and poorly implemented digital interventions that undermine efficiency, usability, and patient safety. The COVID-19 pandemic further exposed these systemic weaknesses, underscoring the urgent need for resilient, digital-first health solutions. This White Paper presents outcomes of a doctoral research project involving nearly 600 clinicians across three tertiary hospitals in Nigeria, which developed the *Tertiary Unified Medical Record for Integrated Care (TUMERIC)*—a cloud-based and voice-enabled electronic health record system designed to align with local clinical workflows. The multiphase study produced an **Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework**, grounded in human-centered design, participatory development, and agile engineering principles. A key contribution is the

TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) model, a policy-aligned, regulator-commended ecosystem optimized for low-bandwidth environments and capable of supporting both synchronous and asynchronous healthcare delivery. Evidence from usability testing confirmed high acceptance by doctors, nurses, medical record officers, and patients, while regulatory recognition was provided by the Health Records Officers Registration Board of Nigeria and the National Information Technology Development Agency. By bridging the gap between policy intent and hospital-level implementation, TUMERIC and TCN provide a scalable pathway to establish a national electronic health record system, strengthen pandemic preparedness, and position Nigeria as a continental leader in digital healthcare transformation.

Keywords: White Paper, Digital Healthcare Transformation, Evidence-Based Framework, Human-Centered Design, TUMERIC, TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN), Nigeria, Cloud-Based Health Systems, Voice-Enabled Clinical Care, Healthcare Policy

2. Executive Summary

Nigeria's healthcare system continues to face systemic challenges rooted in fragmented, paper-based processes and often poorly designed and implemented digital interventions that undermine efficiency, usability, and frustrates overall clinical end-user experience, jeopardize patient safety, and severely encumber continuity of care. The COVID-19 pandemic further exposed and exacerbated these weaknesses, demonstrating the urgent need for digital-first solutions capable of supporting both crisis response and routine healthcare delivery.

This White Paper presents the Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework, the cloud-based and voice-enabled TUMERIC, and the TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) as scalable, evidence-based solutions to accelerate digital healthcare transformation in Nigeria and across Africa's developing economies.

The TUMERIC Contribution

A cloud-based and voice-enabled Tertiary Unified Medical Record for Integrated Care (TUMERIC) was developed through a doctoral research project conducted across three Nigerian tertiary hospitals with nearly 600 clinicians. The entire research process produced an Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework which applies human-centered software engineering, participatory, and agile design principles to create digital health system that aligns with clinical workflows and contextual realities. Part of the contribution of that research was TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) model, which supports cloud-based and voice-enabled ecosystem of healthcare digital infrastructure optimized for low-bandwidth environments, and capable of supporting both synchronous and asynchronous outpatient healthcare management and delivery.

Key Research Evidence

- **High usability and acceptance:** Doctors, nurses, medical record officers, and patients rated TUMERIC as highly usable and workflow-compliant.

- **Collaborative care:** The system enables real-time and asynchronous consultations, mentoring, and peer-to-peer clinical support.
- **Scalability:** The TCN can connect over 200 tertiary healthcare facilities into a single centralized electronic health record (EHR) ecosystem.
- **Regulatory recognition:** Commended by the Health Records Officers Registration Board of Nigeria (HRORBN) and the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA).

Policy and Strategic Relevance

Nigeria has adopted a series of policy instruments — including the *Nigeria Digital in Health Initiative (NDHI)*, *National Cloud Policy* and the *National Health ICT Strategic Framework* — but implementation remains uncoordinated and inconsistent at the hospital level. The TUMERIC model bridges this policy–practice gap by providing a field-tested, locally developed, and regulator-aligned solution ready for national scale-up.

The Policy Ask

Policymakers should leverage the *Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework* and TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) model to:

1. Establish a National Cloud-Based EHR System hosting all tertiary healthcare facilities.
2. Embed human-centered design as a standard for all digital health interventions.
3. Strengthen infrastructure and capacity through targeted investments in broadband, power, and digital training for clinicians.
4. Institutionalize digital health in pandemic preparedness frameworks to ensure resilience.
5. Promote regional adaptation of the TUMERIC model to position Nigeria as a leader in digital health transformation in sub-Saharan Africa.

A Call to Action

The adoption of TUMERIC model represents a unique opportunity for Nigeria to modernize its healthcare system, improve service delivery, and establish itself as a continental hub for digital innovation. By acting decisively, policymakers can ensure that Nigeria transitions from fragmented paper records and inefficient ineffective digital health interventions to a more resilient digital health ecosystem within the next decade.

3. Introduction & Background

3.1 Nigeria's Healthcare Landscape

Nigeria's healthcare system is one of the largest in Africa, yet it remains constrained by inefficiencies, fragmented service delivery, and inadequate infrastructure. Despite housing over 200 tertiary healthcare facilities, most institutions continue to rely on manual, paper-

based recordkeeping and poorly implemented digital health initiatives that compromises continuity of care, slows decision-making, and increases the risk of medical errors.

The absence of a well-structured national electronic health record (EHR) ecosystem hinders even remote clinical collaboration, limits health data use for planning, and weakens Nigeria's ability to deliver equitable, efficient, and quality healthcare at scale.

3.2 COVID-19 as a Catalyst

The **COVID-19 pandemic** magnified these systemic weaknesses. During lockdowns and surges in patient demand:

- Continuity of care was disrupted due to reliance on paper-based and ineffective digital health systems.
- Remote collaboration among clinicians was limited, in fact non-existent.
- Patient monitoring and follow-up were compromised.

These challenges underscored the urgent need for a resilient digital backbone capable of sustaining healthcare delivery during both emergencies and routine operations.

3.3 Policy Commitments and Gaps

Nigeria has made notable strides at the policy level with instruments such as:

- The **National Digital in Health Initiative (NDHI)**;
- The **National Health ICT Strategic Framework**;
- The **National Cloud Policy (NCP)**

However, despite these frameworks, implementation at hospital level has been inconsistent. Many past digital health initiatives failed because they:

- Imported systems not aligned with local workflows;
- Overlooked clinician and patient input in design;
- Suffered from infrastructural limitations (power and broadband);
- Lacked strong change management and sustainability planning.

3.4 Lessons from Other African Countries

Experiences across Africa highlight the risks of non-contextualized digital health adoption:

- **Ethiopia:** Demonstrated strong readiness for EHR adoption but struggled with usability when non-localized systems were deployed.
- **Kenya:** Pilots in public hospitals showed promise but collapsed under scalability pressures due to fragmented implementation approaches.

These cases reinforce the importance of locally developed, evidence-based, and participatory

models for digital health transformation, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa.

3.5 Research Response: The TUMERIC Model

This doctoral research responds directly to Nigeria's pressing digital health challenges. Working with nearly 600 clinicians across three tertiary hospitals — the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital (UNTH), Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTTH), and the National Orthopaedic Hospital Enugu (NOHE) — the study developed and validated the Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework and TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) model.

- The Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework (Figure 1 of this White Paper) provides the guiding principles for participatory, human-centered, and agile digital health system design.
- The TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) offers a cloud-based and voice-enabled, low-bandwidth-optimized digital ecosystem that overcomes the challenges of interoperability in developing contexts, and supports remote collaborative care, and scalability across Nigeria's tertiary healthcare ecosystem.

Together, these innovations offer a tested, regulator-commended solution that bridges the gap between policy intent and practical implementation.

4. The Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework

4.1 Conceptual Foundation

The Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework was developed to address the persistent challenges of low adoption, poor usability, and fragmented implementation that have undermined previous digital health initiatives in Nigeria.

Unlike imported electronic health record (EHR) systems that often fail to adapt to local realities, TUMERIC is grounded in:

- **Human-centered design:** Engaging doctors, nurses, medical records officers, and patients at every stage of design and testing to ensure that end user expectations are satisfied.
- **Participatory approaches:** Ensuring co-creation with clinicians to increase ownership and sustainability.
- **Agile methodology:** Allowing iterative improvement and rapid adaptation to different hospital settings.

This foundation ensures that digital transformation is not only technologically sound but also clinically relevant and culturally appropriate.

4.2 Core Principles

The Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework is guided by four interrelated principles:

1. **Usability First** – Systems must be intuitive, reduce clinician burden, and align with existing workflows.
2. **Inclusivity** – All stakeholders, from doctors to nurses to medical record officers and patients, all participate in system design and adoption.
3. **Scalability** – Solutions are designed for expansion across Nigeria’s ~203 tertiary healthcare facilities.
4. **Resilience** – Systems must remain functional in low-bandwidth and resource-constrained environments and can support resilient healthcare even in uncertain times as recently occasioned by COVID 19 pandemic.

4.3 Key Features of the Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework

The proposed framework for healthcare digital transformation, anchored on the TUMERIC system, is designed to be **evidence-based, context-sensitive, and policy-aligned**. Its distinctive features include:

Figure 1: Proposed Evidence-Based Digital Healthcare Transformation Framework

1. **Stakeholder-Centered and Participatory Development:** Actively involves clinicians, patients, medical records officers, and IT staff in the design and implementation process to ensure ownership, cultural fit, and long-term sustainability.

2. **Human-Centered and Agile Engineering Approach:** Utilizes iterative design cycles and continuous feedback loops to refine usability and ensure alignment with real-world healthcare needs and workflows.
3. **Infrastructure-Aware Architecture:** Incorporates pragmatic considerations such as unreliable power, limited internet access, and the need for continuous availability, while leveraging Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) deployment for scalability and resilience.
4. **Clinical Workflow Integration:** Aligns system functionalities with existing medical practices, ensuring smooth integration into hospital routines without causing workflow disruptions.
5. **Governance, Policy, and Change Management:** Embeds compliance with Nigeria's National Cloud Policy, Nigeria Digital in Health Initiative (NDHI), National Health ICT Strategic Framework and the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), while also supporting leadership engagement, ethical oversight, and structured change management strategies.
6. **Usability Evaluation and Continuous Learning:** Includes systematic usability assessments (e.g., SUS surveys, observational studies) and creates continuous learning loops that allow iterative improvement over time.
7. **Scalability and Interoperability through TCN Model:** Resolves interoperability challenge in developing context; enabling seamless data access across all tertiary hospitals on the network via a unified and centralized medical records operated through a scalable TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN), facilitating national-scale adoption, big health data analytics, and evidence-based policy formulation and decision-making.
8. **Outcome-Driven Orientation:** Ensures that digital transformation efforts translate into measurable health system improvements such as enhanced patient care, resource optimization, and stronger alignment with global health development goals.

4.4 Key Features of TUMERIC

The **Tertiary Unified Medical Record for Integrated Care (TUMERIC)** system embodies the Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework, operationalizing its guiding principles through the following innovations:

- **Cloud and Voice Enablement:** Reduces reliance on manual record-keeping by integrating voice-assisted clinical documentation, while leveraging cloud infrastructure to support nationwide scalability and secure data management.
- **Workflow Alignment:** Designed around the actual clinical processes observed in tertiary hospitals, ensuring seamless integration into daily medical practice without disrupting existing routines.
- **Collaborative Clinical Support:** Provides structured mechanisms for junior doctors

to consult remotely with senior specialists, strengthening mentorship, supervision, and real-time clinical decision-making.

- **Asynchronous Care Delivery:** Facilitates clinician follow-ups and patient engagement without requiring physical presence, thereby expanding access, reducing bottlenecks and cost of needless visit to hospitals, and improving overall efficiency of care.
- **Training and Mentorship Integration:** Embeds features that enable clinician-to-clinician collaboration and continuous professional education, thereby supporting skill transfer, knowledge sharing, and long-term capacity building.

Together, these features position TUMERIC not only as a practical digital health system but also as a scalable, evidence-based framework for advancing sustainable healthcare transformation in Nigeria and other low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

4.5 Key Features of the TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN)

The **TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN)** operationalizes the scalability of the TUMERIC framework by providing a unified, policy-aligned infrastructure for tertiary hospitals nationwide. Its key features include:

- **Unified & Centralized National Database:** A single, cloud-hosted repository for patient records across all tertiary hospitals. This eliminates silos, **resolves interoperability challenges in developing contexts**, and ensures standardized, secure, and consistent data nationwide.
- **Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) Hosting:** Conceptualized and designed for a government-approved cloud infrastructure to comply with Nigeria's National Cloud Policy and NDPR.
*TCN leverages the **native security apparatus of the Cloud Service Provider (CSP)** (e.g., encryption, intrusion detection, automated patching, and compliance certifications).*
- **Scalability across over 200 Tertiary Hospitals:** Designed for nationwide rollout, with phased integration ensuring resilience, load balancing, and high system availability.
- **Collaborative Care Network:** Enables cross-hospital consultations, referrals, and clinician-to-clinician collaboration, fostering knowledge sharing and continuity of care.
- **Advanced Analytics & Decision Support:** Has potential to aggregate nationwide clinical data into a single ecosystem, supporting big health data analytics, predictive modeling, and real-time policy insights.
- **Disaster Recovery & Redundancy:** Supports encrypted backups and failover capabilities across availability zones and safeguard service continuity, leveraging

Cloud Service Providers' (CSP) capabilities.

Governance & Access Control

Role-based access management, two-factor authentication, and audit trails enforce accountability and protect patient privacy.

By centralizing health data, TCN eliminates fragmentation and interoperability challenges, creating a unified national health information ecosystem.

Proposed TUMERIC Cloud Network Model/Architecture based on Proposed Government Cloud Infrastructure

Figure 2: A Proposed TUMERIC Cloud Network Model/Architecture based on Proposed Government Cloud Infrastructure

5. The Research Conceptual Framework Diagram

At the onset the doctoral research was guided by our adopted Conceptual Model/Framework to support our study digital transformation of Nigerian tertiary healthcare, as shown in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: Conceptual model/Framework for digital transformation of Nigerian tertiary healthcare

6. Research Evidence & Validation

The Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework and the TUMERIC Cloud Network were developed and validated through a multi-phase doctoral research study conducted in three major Nigerian tertiary hospitals: the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital (UNTH), Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTTH), and the National Orthopaedic Hospital Enugu (NOHE). Nearly 600 clinicians — including doctors, nurses, and medical records officers — participated through surveys, structured interviews, informal interactions, systems requirements engineering, observations, systems testing and scaled usability evaluation.

6.1 Stakeholder Readiness

- **Moderate to High Digital Readiness:** Surveys revealed that most clinicians believed their hospitals were ready for digital adoption, though with variations across hospitals.
- **Professional Differences:** Doctors clinicians showed stronger willingness to adopt digital tools. Nurses and medical record officers expressed readiness but emphasized

the need for training and ongoing support.

- **Leadership Influence:** Hospital leadership commitment emerged as a decisive factor in successful adoption.

6.2 Barriers to Digital Transformation

The study identified persistent barriers that explain why many past digital health initiatives in Nigeria failed:

- **Infrastructural Gaps:** Unreliable power supply and low broadband penetration.
- **Usability Concerns:** Existing EHR systems were poorly designed and poorly aligned with clinical workflows, frustrating clinicians.
- **Change Management Failures:** Top-down implementations excluded frontline users, resulting in low adoption.
- **Policy-Practice Disconnect:** National policies and strategies often failed to translate into operational systems at hospital level.

6.3 TUMERIC Innovations Implementation

TUMERIC directly addressed these barriers through innovations that combine technical design with contextual usability:

- **Cloud-Based and Voice-Enabled System:** Reduced reliance on typing/manual entry, optimized for low-bandwidth and low digital literacy environments.
- **Collaborative Clinical Support:** Enabled remote expert consultations, allowing junior doctors to seek real-time or asynchronous guidance.
- **Mentorship and Training Features:** TUMERIC fostered clinician-to-clinician knowledge transfer.
- **Asynchronous Care Delivery:** Supported follow-up remote consultations without requiring patient presence, improving efficiency and access.

Figure 4: TUMERIC Home Page

Figure 5: Doctor's activity diagram with TUMERIC

6.4 Usability Testing and Acceptance

- **High Usability Scores:** Doctors, nurses, medical record officers, and patients rated TUMERIC as highly usable and effective, with strong alignment to existing workflows.
- **Positive Clinician Feedback:** Participants appreciated the potentials of voice-based documentation particularly clinicians with low computer literacy.
- **Patient Experience:** Patients valued the prospects of remote engagement with clinicians, helping avoid costs and save time due to unnecessary hospital visits.

6.5 Regulatory and Policy Commendations

The TUMERIC system received commendations from two key regulatory bodies:

- **Health Records Officers Registration Board of Nigeria (HRORBN)** — commended alignment with national digital health strategy and initiatives.
- **National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA)** — recognized TUMERIC as innovative and commended its alignment with national ICT policies and strategies.

These commendations establish policy credibility and demonstrate that TUMERIC is not just a research prototype but a nationally relevant, regulator-aligned innovation.

7. Policy & Practice Implications

The evidence from the TUMERIC research demonstrates that Nigeria stands at a pivotal moment in its healthcare transformation journey. By adopting a locally developed, regulator-aligned digital health framework, Nigeria can bridge the gap between national policy commitments and on-the-ground clinical realities. The following implications highlight why TUMERIC matters for both policy formulation and practical implementation.

7.1 Strengthening National Healthcare Delivery

- **From Fragmentation to Integration:** TUMERIC provides a pathway to unify Nigeria's tertiary hospitals under a national cloud-based EHR system, replacing fragmented paper records and fragmented EHR with seamless digital workflows.
- **Improved Quality of Care:** Unified health records ensure that patient histories are accessible across facilities, reducing errors, duplication, and delays.
- **Efficiency Gains:** Clinicians can collaborate remotely, access patient data instantly, and provide follow-up care more efficiently.

7.2 Advancing Digital Health Policy Commitments

- Alignment with the **National Digital in Health Initiative (NDHI)**, **National Strategic ICT Framework** and the **National Cloud Policy**: TUMERIC operationalizes these

policies' goals by embedding digital tools into daily hospital practice.

- **Bridging the Policy–Practice Divide:** Unlike previous initiatives, TUMERIC is field-tested, user-validated, and regulator-recognized, making it ready for scale-up.

7.3 Building Pandemic Resilience

- **Continuity of Care during Crises:** Cloud and remote patient engagement features ensure that healthcare delivery continues even during lockdowns and mobility restrictions.
- **Digital Triage and Remote Consultations:** By institutionalizing remote care, TUMERIC strengthens Nigeria's pandemic preparedness framework.
- **National Health Security:** A centralized EHR system enhances disease surveillance, outbreak response, and data-driven decision-making.

7.4 Strengthening Human Capacity and Digital Readiness

- **Clinician Empowerment:** By embedding training, mentorship, and usability in its design, TUMERIC and the Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework increases acceptance and confidence among healthcare workers.
- **Workforce Development:** Integration of TUMERIC into medical and nursing training programmes as recently contemplated by one of the policy stakeholders at the HRORBN, would ensure that future generations of clinicians are digitally ready.
- **Leadership Buy-in:** Hospital management support and approvals, which was decisive in this research, further reinforced TUMERIC Framework participatory design principles.

7.5 Positioning Nigeria as a Continental Leader

- **Regional Adaptability:** TUMERIC addresses the infrastructural and usability constraints common across African developing economies.
- **ECOWAS and African Union Alignment:** Nigeria can lead in shaping cross-country digital health record interoperability resolution frameworks.
- **Global Recognition:** A successful nationwide TUMERIC on TCN rollout would position Nigeria as a benchmark for digital health transformation in resource-constrained settings.

7.6 Practical Implications for Stakeholders

- **For Policymakers:** Provides a scalable, regulator-friendly solution for operationalizing NDHI, NCP and National Strategic ICT Framework objectives.
- **For Hospital Administrators:** Offers a tested model to increase efficiency, reduce cost, reduce delays, improve access and improve patient satisfaction.
- **For Development Partners and Donors:** Represents an investment-ready digital

health model with proven usability and scalability.

8. National and Regional Implementation Roadmap

To transform Nigeria's tertiary healthcare system into a digital-first ecosystem, the Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework, the TUMERIC and TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) should be adopted through a phased approach. This ensures feasibility, scalability, and long-term sustainability.

8.1 Short-Term (1–2 Years)

Goal: Establish proof of concept and regulatory alignment

- **Pilot Projects:** Have 3–5 federally funded tertiary hospitals across different geopolitical zones subscribe to the TUMERIC on TUMERIC Cloud Network.
- **Regulatory Frameworks:** Finalize national policies on EHR data standards, interoperability, and cybersecurity.
- **Capacity Building:** Launch targeted training programs for doctors, nurses, medical records officers and other key clinical stakeholders in pilot hospitals.
- **Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs):** Collaborate with telecom providers, power companies, and cloud service firms, and partner with appropriate government agency to operationalize National Cloud Policy via government cloud infrastructure in order to secure sufficient infrastructure support.
- **Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E):** Establish an independent Digital Health Evaluation Unit within the Federal Ministry of Health to track adoption progress.

8.2 Medium-Term (3–5 Years)

Goal: Scale adoption nationally while ensuring quality

- **National Rollout:** Expand TUMERIC Cloud Network deployment to more federal and state teaching hospitals (~100 institutions subscription to TUMERIC SaaS cloud platform).
- **Incentivize Adoption:** Provide subsidies, grants, and technical assistance for hospitals achieving EHR subscription milestones.
- **Local Innovation Hubs:** Establish Digital Health Innovation Centers in teaching hospitals to foster clinician-driven improvements.
- **Policy Enforcement:** Make compliance with national EHR standards a prerequisite for government ICT funding in healthcare.

8.3 Long-Term (5–10 Years)

Goal: Achieve nationwide integration and regional leadership

- **Full National Integration:** Connect all ~203 tertiary hospitals to the TUMERIC Cloud

Network, creating a centralized, cloud-native national EHR system.

- **Advanced Analytics & AI:** Leverage aggregated EHR data for predictive health planning, AI-driven diagnostics, and national health intelligence.
- **Pandemic Preparedness:** Institutionalize TUMERIC as part of Nigeria's national health emergency response infrastructure.
- **Regional Scaling:** Sell/promote TUMERIC model to other neighbouring West African countries through ECOWAS partnerships.
- **Global Recognition:** Establish Nigeria as a regional leader in digital health transformation, sharing best practices globally.

9. Conclusion

Nigeria's healthcare system is at a crossroads. The persistence of fragmented, paper-based and often poorly implemented digital processes continues to undermine efficiency, quality of care, and preparedness for future health emergencies. Yet, the evidence presented in this research demonstrates that sustainable, locally developed digital health solutions are both possible and urgently needed.

The Evidence-Based Healthcare Digital Transformation Framework and TUMERIC Cloud Network (TCN) provide a rare opportunity to leapfrog systemic barriers by combining human-centered design, participatory development, and cloud-enabled technologies. Validated across three tertiary hospitals and commended by national regulators, the model is uniquely positioned for national adoption and continental influence.

Adopting this model would:

- Establish a centralized national electronic health record system that connects ~203 tertiary hospitals;
- Improve efficiency, collaboration, and patient outcomes;
- Embed digital resilience into Nigeria's pandemic preparedness framework;
- Position Nigeria as a continental leader in digital health innovation, offering a scalable model adaptable across Africa's developing economies.

The window of opportunity is now. Delays in digital adoption risk entrenching inefficiencies and limiting Nigeria's competitiveness in the global health landscape. By acting decisively — starting with pilots, scaling nationally, and extending regionally — Nigeria can modernize its healthcare system, safeguard its citizens, and lead Africa into a new era of digital health transformation.